

Vibration Analysis of Multi-Span Nonhomogeneous Beam

Duygu Dönmez Demir^{*1}, B. Gültekin Sınır², Emine Kahraman³
¹Manisa Celal Bayar University, Dept. of Mathematics, Manisa, Türkiye
²Manisa Celal Bayar University, Dept. of Civil Engineering, Manisa, Türkiye
³Manisa Celal Bayar University, Manisa Teknocity, Manisa, Türkiye
**Corresponding author: duygu.donmez@cbu.edu.tr*

Abstract

Vibration analysis of a multi-span nonhomogeneous beam involves studying the dynamic behavior of the beam under different loading and boundary conditions. Nonhomogeneous beams have varying material properties along their length, which adds complexity to the analysis compared to homogeneous beams. Mathematical modelling describes the geometry of the beam, including length, cross-sectional properties, and variations in material properties and expresses the material properties as functions of the spatial coordinates, considering variations in stiffness, density, and other relevant parameters. The equation of motion for the nonhomogeneous beam based on the chosen beam theory is derived. The equation should include terms related to bending, shear, and axial deformation. The eigenvalue problem to obtain the natural frequencies and mode shapes of the nonhomogeneous beam is solved. To perform modal analysis, numerical methods or software tools are considered.

Keywords: Multi-span beams, nonhomogeneous beam

Introduction

Multi-span beams are structural elements that extend across multiple supports, commonly found in bridges, buildings, and various engineering applications. These beams play a critical role in distributing loads over several supports, which enhances the overall stability and performance of structures. However, the complexity of their behavior increases significantly when they exhibit inhomogeneity, meaning their material properties or cross-sectional dimensions vary along their length.

The nonhomogeneous beams, also known as non-uniform or heterogeneous beams, are characterized by variations in properties such as elasticity, density, and geometry. These variations can arise from intentional design choices, such as the use of different materials along the beam to optimize performance, or from unavoidable factors like material defects and environmental influences. The analysis and design of multi-span inhomogeneous beams require advanced theoretical and computational approaches to accurately predict their response under various loading conditions.

The study of multi-span inhomogeneous beams involves understanding how these variations affect the beam's structural behavior, including deflection, internal forces, and stress distribution. Traditional beam theories, such as Euler-Bernoulli and Timoshenko beam theories, are often extended or modified to account for the inhomogeneity. Numerical methods, such as the finite element method (FEM), are frequently employed to handle the increased complexity and provide detailed insights into the performance of these beams.

Research in this area focuses on material nonhomogeneity, geometric nonhomogeneity, analytical and numerical methods and engineering applications. Mikata [1] considers the exact closed-form solution of its mathematical model for analysing the vibrations of a two-span Bernoulli-Euler beam. Lin [2] applies numerical assembly method to examine behavior of a multi-span uniform beam carrying a number of various concentrated elements. Dönmez Demir et. al. [3] consider the dynamic behaviors of beams modeled by using linear spring element which is called Winkler type foundation. They [4] investigate advantages in the numerical solution of the structural element model containing any discontinuity. [5] introduce the orthogonality condition for a multi-span beam, and its application to forced (transient) vibration of a two-span beam. Wang et. al. [6] present the finite-difference model and the corresponding stiffness matrix for an arbitrarily supported multi-span beam. Recently, Liu et. al. proposes an analytical calculation method for the dynamic response of multi-span bridge-track structure systems under the action of moving load series. Li et. al. [8] investigate the vibration characteristics of multi-span beams resting on an elastic foundation and subjected to axial forces.

This study focuses on the vibration analysis of multi-span beams with heterogeneous structural characteristics. To analyze such a system, instead of writing a single equation containing a singular function for multi-span beams, separate equations can be written for each span. This performs it easier for us to solve the problem. The analytical method is used for solution.

Equation of Motion

In this section, we will consider the mathematical model for a multi-span nonhomogeneous beam. Then, the equation of motion [9] is

$$\text{I. Region: } \tilde{E}_1 \tilde{I} \tilde{w}_1^{iv} + \tilde{P} \tilde{w}_1'' + \tilde{\rho}_1 \tilde{A} \tilde{\ddot{w}}_1 = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{II. Region: } \tilde{E}_2 \tilde{I} \tilde{w}_2^{iv} + \tilde{P} \tilde{w}_2'' + \tilde{\rho}_2 \tilde{A} \tilde{\ddot{w}}_2 = 0 \quad (2)$$

where \tilde{w} , \tilde{E} , \tilde{I} , \tilde{P} , \tilde{A} , $\tilde{\rho}$ represent displacement, modulus of elasticity, moment of inertia, axial load, cross-sectional area and density of material, respectively. The notations $(\cdot)'$ and $(\cdot)''$ indicate the derivative with respect to the spatial, x and time, t along the beam. Then, a beam with two span is considered as two separate regions as shown in the following.

Figure 1. Multi-Span nonhomogeneous beam

To eliminate the dependence on shape and material, applying a process of nondimensionalization into the equations (1) and (2) yields

$$w_1^{iv} + P \cdot w_1'' + \dot{w}_1 = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\alpha_{E_2} w_2^{iv} + P \cdot w_2'' + \alpha_{\rho_2} \dot{w}_2 = 0 \quad (4)$$

where the dimensionless terms are

$$w = \frac{\tilde{w}_i L}{r^2}, \quad t = \frac{\tilde{t}}{L^2} \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{E}_1 \tilde{I}}{\rho \tilde{A}}}, \quad x = \frac{\tilde{x}}{L}, \quad r = \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{I}}{\tilde{A}}}, \quad P = \frac{\tilde{P}(\tilde{E}_1 \tilde{I})}{L^2}, \quad \alpha_{E_2} = \frac{\tilde{E}_2}{\tilde{E}_1}, \quad \alpha_{\rho_2} = \frac{\tilde{\rho}_2}{\tilde{\rho}_1} \quad (5)$$

The boundary conditions for the dimensionless equation for simple-simple support are given as follows;

$$\begin{aligned} w_1(0, t) &= 0 \\ w_2(1, t) &= 0 \\ w_1''(0, t) &= 0 \\ w_2''(1, t) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

In the transition region, the displacement equals to zero at the simple-simple support, rotation and bending moment are equal for $x_i = x_1$. Then, the transition conditions are presented in the form

$$\begin{aligned} w_1(x_1, t) &= 0 \\ w_2(x_1, t) &= 0 \\ w_1'(x_1, t) &= w_2'(x_1, t) \\ w_1''(x_1, t) &= \alpha_{E_2} w_2''(x_1, t) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Solutions

In this section, the solutions of the linear equations given for the first and second regions will be considered. Substituting the solution suggestion

$$w_1(x) = X_1(x) \cdot e^{i\omega_n t} \quad (8)$$

into Eq. (3) for the first region and

$$w_2(x) = X_2(x) \cdot e^{i\omega_n t} \quad (9)$$

into equation (4) for the second region, one obtains

$$X_1^{iv}(x) + P X_1''(x) - \omega_n^2 X_1(x) = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\alpha_{E_2} X_2^{iv}(x) + P X_2''(x) - \alpha_{\rho_2} \omega_n^2 X_2(x) = 0 \quad (11)$$

respectively, where the boundary conditions are reformulated as

$$\begin{aligned} X_1(0) &= 0 \\ X_2(1) &= 0 \\ X_1''(0) &= 0 \\ X_2''(1) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

and the transient conditions are rearranged as

$$X_1(x_1) = 0, X_2(x_1) = 0, X_1'(x_1) = X_2'(x_1), X_1''(x_1) = X_2''(x_1) \quad (13)$$

Solving Eq. (10) in the 1st region gives

$$X_1(x) = c_1 e^{r_1 x} + c_2 e^{r_2 x} + c_3 e^{r_3 x} + c_4 e^{r_4 x} \quad (14)$$

where the characteristic equation is

$$r^4 + Pr^2 - \omega_n^2 = 0 \quad (15)$$

If the obtained 4th-degree polynomial is solved, then the roots of the characteristic equation are as

$$r_{1,2,3,4} = \pm \frac{\sqrt{\pm 2\sqrt{P^2 + 4\omega_n^2} - 2P}}{2} \quad (16)$$

Similarly, the solution of differential equation (11) is written as

$$X_2(x) = a_1 e^{b_1 x} + a_2 e^{b_2 x} + a_3 e^{b_3 x} + a_4 e^{b_4 x} \quad (17)$$

for the second region. Thus, the characteristic equation becomes

$$\alpha_{E_2} b^4 + Pb^2 - \alpha_{\rho_2} \omega_n^2 = 0 \quad (18)$$

where the roots are

$$b_{1,2,3,4} = \pm \frac{\sqrt{\pm 2\alpha_{E_2} \left(-P + \sqrt{4\alpha_{E_2} \alpha_{\rho_2} \omega_n^2 + P^2} \right)}}{2\alpha_{E_2}} \quad (19)$$

Numerical Results

In this section, we will consider the natural frequencies and the values of the critical P load for different materials. The values, α_{E_1} and α_{ρ_1} for all examples will be of the form ($\alpha_{E_1} = 1, \alpha_{\rho_1} = 1$).

Table 1. The natural frequencies for aluminum and copper ($\alpha_{E_2} = 2, \alpha_{\rho_2} = 1$)

x_1	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9
$P = 0$	24.08422991	34.40958913	46.41022050	28.18890055	18.39442909
$P = 5$	22.68051912	32.77997459	44.21049112	26.17007496	16.40782922
$P = 10$	21.17984752	31.06155477	41.89454903	23.97552163	14.12542044
$P = 20$	17.78627538	27.28934225	36.82505118	18.80620715	7.622167359

Table 2. Variation of critical value of P for aluminum and copper

x_1	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9
P	43.61549875	53.44089607	53.90486275	35.82540860	24.03938663

Table 3. The natural frequencies for aluminum and steel ($\alpha_{E_2} = 3, \alpha_{\rho_2} = 3$)

x_1	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9
$P = 0$	54.85689675	23.41301762	61.67282287	29.00248662	60.30642207
$P = 2$	54.55197090	23.09365679	61.04887268	28.23070147	59.43947144
$P = 5$	54.09137908	22.60544795	60.10662097	27.02958643	58.11458104
$P = 7$	53.78214090	22.27353419	59.47434050	26.19671670	57.21416199

Table 4. Variation of critical value of P for aluminum and steel

x_1	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9
P	61.92964844	71.63009307	61.78713986	37.48497630	71.89079517

Conclusion

Considering the numerical results, natural frequency values are found for various axial load values, P in beams consisted of different materials and for different section lengths. It has been observed that as the axial load values, P increase, the natural frequency value decreases. Thus, as the natural frequency decreases, the stiffness will also decrease. Afterwards, the critical value, P was calculated according to the section lengths of the regions. The critical load is the smallest value that causes the beam to buckle. It is seen that as the critical axial load increases, the natural frequency decreases.

References

- [1] Mikata Y. Analytical solution for a two-span beam vibration. National Technical Reports Library,
- [2] Knolls Atomic Power Lab., Schenectady, NY.; Department of Energy, Washington, DC.; 2006.
- [3] Lin, H-Y. Dynamic analysis of a multi-span uniform beam carrying a number of various concentrated elements. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*. 2008; 309(1-2): 262-275.
- [4] Dönmez Demir D, Sınır BG, Kahraman E. (2019). The solution of the governing equation of the beam on linear spring foundation modeled by a discontinuity function. *Sigma: Journal of Engineering & Natural Sciences*. 2019; 37(2):495-506.
- [5] Dönmez Demir D, Sınır BG, Kahraman E. Dynamical analysis of the general beam model with singularity function. *Journal of Engineering Research*. 2021; 9(3A):52-63.
- [6] Mikata Y. Orthogonality condition for a multi-span beam, and its application to transient vibration of a two-span beam. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 2008; 314(3-5): 851-866.
- [7] Wang QS, Wang DJ, Wu L, Zhang LH, Jiang YY. Qualitative properties of frequencies and modes of vibrating multi-span beam. *Quarterly journal of mechanics and applied mathematics*. 2011; 64(1): 75-86.
- [8] Liu S, Jiang L, Zhou W, Xilin C, Zhang Y. Dynamic response analysis of multi-span bridge-track structure system under moving loads. *Mechanics Based Design of Structures and Machines*. 2023; 51(10): 5669-5687.
- [9] Li J, Chen B, Mao H. Exact closed-form solution for vibration characteristics of multi-span beams on an elastic foundation subjected to axial force. In *Structures* 2024; 60: 105884.
- [10] Dönmez Demir D, Sınır BG. Singüleriye fonksiyonları ile modellenen yapı elemanlarının dinamik analizine yeni bir yaklaşım. Manisa Celal Bayar University. BAP Project 2018; Project Number: 2016-113.